

Post-diction analysis of an unreinforced masonry building aggregate using the Discrete Macro-Element Method

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Abstract

Unreinforced masonry (URM) aggregate buildings constitute a significant portion of the European built heritage and are widely distributed in historic urban centres. Their seismic assessment remains particularly challenging due to geometric irregularities, material heterogeneity, and the complex interaction mechanisms between adjacent structural units. In this context, the SERA-AIMS experimental campaign provides a valuable benchmark for the validation of numerical modelling strategies through shaking table tests on a half-scale masonry aggregate.

This study presents a post-diction analysis of the SERA-AIMS specimen using a three-dimensional Discrete Macro-Element Method (DMEM) model implemented in the HiStrA software. The numerical model is calibrated on the basis of available experimental data and further refined through sensitivity analyses aimed at assessing the influence of the most relevant mechanical parameters on the structural response. Nonlinear analyses, including Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) and pushover analysis, are performed to investigate the seismic behaviour of the prototype.

The results show that the proposed model is able to reproduce the global response of the specimen with satisfactory accuracy, particularly in terms of base shear and failure mechanisms, while maintaining limited computational demand. However, the model tends to underestimate displacement demand at high seismic intensity levels. Overall, the study confirms the potential of the DMEM approach as an efficient numerical tool for the seismic assessment of masonry aggregates, while also highlighting the need for further developments to improve the prediction of displacement capacity and damage evolution.

Keywords: masonry aggregate buildings, nonlinear dynamic analysis, Discrete Macro-Element Method, Incremental Dynamic Analysis, sensitivity analysis, post-diction analysis.

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1. Introduction

Unreinforced masonry (URM) aggregate buildings represent a widespread structural typology in European historic city centres, and their well-known seismic vulnerability continues to attract growing attention within structural engineering. The assessment of these structures remains particularly challenging because of their pronounced heterogeneity and geometric complexity, as illustrated in Fig. 1. This complexity mainly derives from two factors. First, historic urban settlements generally developed in a spontaneous and unplanned manner, without codified urban design criteria. Second, the progressive superposition of construction phases and structural modifications over time has often altered the original structural configuration of the buildings.

The scarcity of buildable land historically favoured two main construction processes: the vertical expansion of existing buildings and the addition of new units adjacent to pre-existing ones. As a result, building aggregates developed as highly interconnected systems characterised by material continuity, limited spacing between façades, and irregular plan layouts. Under these conditions, individual buildings lose their identity as isolated structural entities and instead become part of a wider structural organism. The presence of shared walls and physical continuity between adjacent units generates structural interdependence, which is the defining feature of aggregate configurations.

According to the Italian technical standard (NTC 2018, Italian Ministry of Infrastructure, §C8.7.1.3.2), the study of aggregate buildings should begin with the identification of its constituent Structural Units (SUs). According to the guidelines for masonry aggregates issued by the Rete dei Laboratori Universitari di Ingegneria Sismica e strutturale (ReLUIS 2010), SUs must exhibit vertical continuity from roof to foundation in order to ensure a continuous load path under gravity loads. In general, a SU is bounded by open spaces, structural joints, or adjacent buildings with different construction and structural characteristics. However, in historic urban fabrics, the identification of each SUs is often far from straightforward because of the intrinsic ambiguity of structural continuity.

A reliable interpretation of the structural behaviour of these building aggregate therefore requires a detailed historical and constructive analysis, which is also essential for the correct identification of the constituent units. From the standpoint of construction genesis, SUs may be classified as pre-existing units, growth units, or saturation units (Cima et al. 2024). Pre-existing units are originally independent buildings later incorporated into the aggregate; growth units are added afterwards through vertical enlargement or horizontal expansion; and saturation units are built to fill the spaces between pre-existing or growth units. Structural units may also be classified according to their position within the aggregate, for example as end, corner, interlocking, projecting, or dual-facing units, or according to their elevation condition, such as towering, enclosed, or aligned units. Although this classification is useful as a preliminary qualitative tool for identifying potentially vulnerable units, it is not sufficient on its own. A reliable seismic assessment requires the integration of these geometric aspects with additional factors that govern the overall response of the aggregate (Pinasco et al. 2025).

Once the constituent SUs have been identified, it becomes essential to assess the mechanical interaction among adjacent units. In this regard, each SU should not be regarded as an independent structural system, since its

response in isolation is not representative of its actual behaviour within the aggregate. The seismic performance of aggregate buildings is governed by interaction mechanisms between contiguous units, which may significantly modify both local and global response (Greco et al. 2020). Despite the considerable research effort devoted to this issue, the literature still lacks a unified consensus on whether the so-called aggregate effect, namely the structural interaction between adjacent units, is beneficial or detrimental to seismic performance, except in relatively simple cases such as corner or end units.

Today, the widespread presence of historic building aggregates within the urban fabric represents not only an important expression of built cultural heritage, but also a major engineering challenge in the definition of reliable assessment strategies and sustainable retrofitting interventions. The development of dependable numerical procedures for their analysis has long been hindered by the limited availability of experimental data on their seismic response. In recent years, however, the growing relevance of this topic and the need to validate computational approaches have led to important experimental initiatives.

A major contribution in this field was provided by the Adjacent Interacting Masonry Structures (AIMS) project (Tomić et al. 2024a), which included a blind prediction exercise on a two-unit stone masonry aggregate tested on the shaking table at the National Laboratory for Civil Engineering (LNEC) in Portugal. Thirteen research groups participated in the blind prediction competition, adopting different modelling approaches, including Equivalent Frame Models (EFM) (Tomić and Beyer 2024), Finite Element Models (FEM) (Aşıkoğlu et al. 2024; Ramaglia et al. 2024; Bianchini et al. 2024), Discrete Element Models (DEM) (Malomo et al. 2024; Galvez et al. 2024; AlShawa et al. 2024), as well as hybrid and limit-analysis-based formulations (Gagliardo et al. 2024). None of the submitted models adopted the Discrete Macro-Element Method (DMEM), although this approach offers a promising balance between computational efficiency and accuracy in the nonlinear simulation of masonry structures.

Within this framework, the present study addresses the post-diction analysis of the AIMS benchmark by developing a numerical model based on the DMEM, implemented in the HiStrA software (Gruppo Sismica s.r.l. 2024). The main objective is to evaluate the capability of the DMEM to reproduce the seismic response of URM aggregate buildings and, in particular, to capture the interaction between adjacent units by comparison with the corresponding experimental results. The study shows that the adopted approach is able to provide a realistic prediction of base shear response and failure mechanisms, accounting for both in-plane (IP) and out-of-plane (OOP) behaviour. At the same time, the analyses highlight current modelling limitations, especially in nonlinear dynamic simulations, which tend to underestimate displacement capacity at high PGA levels.

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 summarises the main features of the DMEM modelling strategy adopted in this study. Section 3 describes the SERA-AIMS experimental campaign. Section 4 presents the calibration procedure of the numerical model. Section 5 discusses the numerical results and their comparison with the experimental evidence, including Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) and dynamic pushover analysis. Finally, Section 6 summarises the main conclusions.

Fig. 1 a) Examples of URM aggregate buildings located in the city of Catania (Italy); **b)** Detailed view of Aggregate 2 highlighting its constituent SUs

2. Discrete Macro-Element Method

Over the past decades, several numerical approaches have been developed for the nonlinear analysis of masonry structures. However, their application to masonry buildings within aggregates still raises important challenges, mainly due to the need to capture both the nonlinear behaviour of masonry and the interaction between adjacent structural units. These approaches differ not only in their theoretical formulation, but also in the scale adopted to represent masonry, ranging from equivalent continuum models to block-based and fully discrete descriptions.

In Finite Element Method (FEM)-based formulations, masonry can be described either as a homogenised continuum through macro-modelling approaches or by explicitly representing units and mortar joints through micro-modelling techniques. Discrete Element Method (DEM)-based approaches, by contrast, represent masonry as an assemblage of distinct interacting blocks connected through nonlinear interfaces. Although both strategies offer considerable modelling flexibility and a detailed description of the structural response, they are generally associated with high computational demand, especially in nonlinear dynamic analyses, where the large number of degrees of freedom may become a limiting factor.

To overcome these limitations, a discrete macro-element strategy has been proposed as an efficient alternative for the seismic analysis of masonry structures. The Discrete Macro-Element Method (DMEM), originally proposed by Calìo et al. (2012), provides a suitable balance between computational efficiency and predictive capability. The method idealises masonry as an assemblage of macro-elements specifically conceived to reproduce its main nonlinear mechanisms with a limited number of kinematic variables. As a result, the DMEM is particularly attractive for the analysis of complex structures, such as masonry aggregates, for which a reliable yet computationally manageable numerical strategy is required.

In its original two-dimensional formulation (Fig. 2a), the DMEM macro-element consists of an articulated quadrilateral composed of four rigid edges connected by hinged vertices and two nonlinear diagonal springs, which simulate the in-plane shear response of masonry. The interaction between adjacent elements, or between

the element and the foundation, is governed by discrete zero-thickness nonlinear interfaces located along the edges, where axial and flexural deformability is concentrated. This formulation was later extended to three-dimensional applications (Fig. 2b) in order to simulate the out-of-plane response of masonry structures. In the spatial macro-element, the interaction with adjacent elements is governed by a diagonal spring and three-dimensional zero-thickness interfaces including nonlinear normal springs as well as in-plane and out-of-plane longitudinal springs. Accordingly, the kinematics of the spatial element is described by seven Lagrangian parameters, namely the six rigid-body motions in space and one in-plane shear deformability parameter. This reduced set of governing variables significantly limits the number of degrees of freedom required to describe the structural response, thus reducing the computational effort compared with continuum-based approaches. A further advantage of the DMEM lies in the relative simplicity of its calibration procedure. The model relies on a limited number of macroscopic mechanical parameters, such as elastic moduli, strength properties, and fracture energies, which can be derived from standard laboratory or in situ tests. Moreover, the orthotropic behaviour, typically exhibited by masonry, can be explicitly accounted for by assigning different mechanical properties to vertical and horizontal interfaces. This feature is particularly useful for regular masonry textures, where the mechanical response along bed joints and head joints may differ significantly. A detailed description of the calibration procedure is reported in Pantò et al. (2017).

Fig. 2 Springs layout in the **a)** 2D and **b)** 3D macro-element

According to the DMEM strategy, the nonlinear springs must therefore be calibrated consistently with the macroscopic mechanical properties of the masonry material. This modelling strategy makes the DMEM particularly suitable for engineering applications requiring an effective compromise between modelling detail, numerical robustness, and computational efficiency.

3. Description of the SERA-AIMS experimental campaign

To validate the numerical model developed through the DMEM and implemented in HiStrA, this study considers the results of the SERA-AIMS experimental campaign, carried out at the LNEC laboratory in Portugal in 2021. The programme involved shaking table tests on a half-scale stone masonry aggregate designed to represent the typical features of irregular, non-box-like masonry buildings in historic centres. Before the experimental campaign, twelve research groups participated in a blind prediction competition using different modelling strategies. After the completion of the tests, the numerical predictions were compared with

the experimental evidence and subsequently refined through post-diction analyses to improve the agreement with the observed structural response.

The tested specimen consisted of a half-scale unreinforced masonry aggregate composed of two interacting units. Unit 1 was a single-storey structure with a wall thickness of 30 cm, whereas Unit 2 was a two-storey structure with wall thicknesses equal to 35 cm at the first storey and 25 cm at the second storey. From a constructive point of view, Unit 2 represented the pre-existing unit, while Unit 1 was added later as a growth unit and connected to Unit 2 along Façade 5. To reproduce a typical historic masonry construction, the walls were built as double-leaf irregular stone masonry without transverse connections between the leaves. In addition, the interface between the two units was intentionally realised as a weak connection, consisting only of a layer of NHL 2.0 mortar without interlocking stones, in order to simulate a common condition found in historical masonry aggregates. The adopted materials were selected to reproduce those previously characterised in experimental studies by Guerrini et al. (2017), whose results also provided the mechanical parameters used in the blind prediction phase for the calibration of the numerical models.

The floors consisted of deformable timber diaphragms, with beam orientations differing in the two units. The beams were simply supported on the masonry walls, with variable support lengths depending on the elevation. To reproduce realistic gravity loads, an additional mass of 1500 kg, consisting of steel plates and concrete bags, was uniformly distributed at each floor level of Unit 2. Finally, a plaster coating was applied to the specimen to facilitate the visual identification of cracking and failure mechanisms during the tests. A three-dimensional view and the plan layout of the specimen are shown in Fig. 3.

The experimental setup included a comprehensive monitoring system composed of accelerometers and additional displacement measurement devices used to record both foundation accelerations and absolute and relative displacements. Particular attention was devoted to the response of the interface between the two units. The opening of the mortar joint was monitored through pairs of Optotrak LED displacement sensors positioned at different elevations, with each sensor located 10 cm from the joint. Since the Optotrak system records absolute spatial coordinates, the relative interface opening at each time step was obtained from the differential displacement between each sensor pair. A detailed description of the instrumentation layout is provided in Tomić et al. (2024a).

Fig. 3 3D view of the specimen and plan geometry (all dimensions in cm)

3.1. Seismic input and loading protocol

The specimen was subjected to both unidirectional and bidirectional seismic excitations using the horizontal components of the 1979 Montenegro earthquake recorded at the Ulcinj–Hotel Albatros station. The east–west component was adopted as the longitudinal input, while the north–south component was applied in the transverse direction. The original test programme initially considered four loading steps, corresponding to 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of the shaking table longitudinal capacity. However, the actual loading sequence adopted during the campaign was more articulated and eventually consisted of ten runs, as reported in Table 1. Since the prototype was built at half-scale, the input signals were time-scaled by a factor of 0.707 according to similarity requirements. The processed acceleration time histories are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Processed acceleration time histories of the Montenegro 1979 earthquake recorded at the Ulcinj – Hotel Albatros station, with unscaled (in red) and scaled (in blue) time step: **a)** east–west component; **b)** north–south component

Table 1 Actual testing sequence (Tomić et al. 2024a)

ID Run	Direction	Level of shaking (w.r.t. longitudinal table capacity)	Actual PGA (direction) [g]
Un – strengthened specimen			
0.1	Longitudinal	12.5%	0.113 (Y)
0.2	Transversal	12.5%	0.075 (X)
0.3	Bidirectional	12.5%	0.114 (Y); 0.072 (X)
1.1	Longitudinal	25%	0.170 (Y)
1.2	Transversal	25%	0.178 (X)
1.3	Bidirectional	25%	0.208 (Y); 0.174 (X)
2.1	Longitudinal	50%	0.593 (Y)
Strengthened specimen			
2.1S	Longitudinal	50%	0.615 (Y)
1.2S	Transversal	25%	0.258 (X)
2.2S	Transversal	50%	0.425 (X)

3.2. Experimental test results

During the first three runs (0.1, 0.2, and 0.3), no significant structural damage was observed. Following Runs 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3, cracking developed mainly at the interface between the two units, where a maximum sliding of 2.7 mm and a maximum crack opening of 1.45 mm were recorded after Run 1.3.

A substantial increase in damage occurred after Run 2.1. In particular, an in-plane flexural-rocking mechanism developed in the upper storey of Façades 2 and 3 of Unit 2. At the same time, out-of-plane cracking was observed at the first-floor level of Façade 4 and at the roof level of Unit 1 along Façade 5. The corresponding crack pattern is shown in Fig. 5. To prevent possible damage to the shaking table due to the onset of collapse after Run 2.1, reinforcement measures consisting of steel connections between the floor beams and the walls were subsequently installed in Unit 2.

After the strengthening intervention, three additional runs were performed (2.1S, 1.2S, and 2.2S). Following Run 2.1S, previously formed cracks widened and additional cracking appeared in Façade 5 and at the first storey of Façade 4, although no full collapse mechanism was triggered. After Run 1.2S, no significant increase in damage was observed. During the final run, 2.2S, no further crack development occurred in Unit 2; however, pronounced in-plane and out-of-plane failure mechanisms developed in Unit 1, particularly in Façade 1 and in the Façade 2–3, as shown in Fig. 6. In quantitative terms, the largest longitudinal opening at the interface, equal to 20.69 mm, was recorded after Run 2.1, whereas the maximum sliding, equal to 5.40 mm, was observed after Run 2.2S. After the final run, the tests were interrupted because of the severe damage sustained by the specimen and the risk of global collapse.

For completeness, Fig. 7 reports the time histories of base shear and displacement recorded, during Runs 2.1 and 2.2S, at one selected control point for each Unit indicated with a red dot in the figure. For each run, the reported response component corresponds to the direction of the applied seismic input. These results provide a useful experimental benchmark for assessing the capability of numerical models to reproduce both the global and local response of masonry aggregates under seismic loading.

Fig. 5 Crack maps after Run 2.1 (Tomić et al. 2024a)

Fig. 6 Crack maps after Run 2.2S (Tomić et al. 2024a)

Fig. 7 Time histories of: **a)** base shear and **b)** displacement in the longitudinal direction (V_{by} , U_y) during Run 2.1; **c)** base shear (V_{bx}) and **d)** displacement in the transversal direction (V_{bx} , U_x) during Run 2.2S

4. Implementation of the DMEM model in HiStrA

This section presents the main features of the numerical model developed for the analysed building aggregate and describes the adopted calibration procedure. As previously noted, the model was implemented in the HiStrA software (Gruppo Sismica s.r.l. 2024), which implements the three-dimensional formulation of the DMEM.

The mesh was defined to ensure a reasonable compromise between computational efficiency and the capability of capturing the most relevant IP and OOP wall mechanisms. Each masonry panel, including both piers and spandrels, was discretised approximately through a 2×2 mesh of macro-elements. Overall, the numerical model consists of 721 macro-elements corresponding to a total of 5047 degrees of freedom only. Macro-elements were used to model both masonry components and timber floor beams; for the latter, an elastic constitutive behaviour was assigned. The interfaces between adjacent masonry macro-elements were discretised through 10 parallel rows of springs along the wall thickness, with a maximum spacing of 400 mm along the panel edge. This modelling choice was adopted to balance numerical accuracy and computational cost. Some simplifying assumptions were introduced in the model. First, the contribution of the floor decking to the overall structural response was neglected and these elements were therefore not included. Second, a support length of 12 cm was assumed for all timber beams. In addition, the timber-to-masonry interaction along the vertical beam faces, considered negligible, has been neglected and the corresponding interface elements were not generated. Finally, neither the foundation system nor the steel elements located above it were explicitly modelled.

Fig. 8 3D view of the numerical model in HiStrA and control points selected

As regards the boundary conditions, the base of the prototype was constrained through a surface restraint in order to reproduce the clamped conditions provided experimentally by the fastening system connecting the specimen to the shaking table. Concerning the applied loads, the self-weight of the masonry walls, timber beams, and lintels was directly derived from the specific weight of the materials. The additional masses placed in Unit 2 were modelled as line loads applied at the beam heads over a length of 12 cm. A three-dimensional view of the final numerical model and the selected control points in which the response is measured, is shown in Fig. 8.

4.1. Model Calibration

According to the DMEM strategy, different constitutive laws were adopted to simulate the nonlinear rocking, diagonal-shear, and sliding-shear behaviour of masonry. Each nonlinear spring inherits the constitutive relationship associated with the corresponding resisting mechanism, and the relevant parameters are derived from the macroscopic material properties through the calibration procedures described by Pantò et al. (2017) and Chácara et al. (2018, 2019).

More specifically, the axial response of masonry under tension and compression was described by an elastoplastic constitutive law with softening. For tensile behaviour, unloading was assumed to be directed towards the origin, while in compression an initial unloading stiffness was adopted (Fig. 9a). The diagonal-shear response was represented through a trilinear constitutive law, again with initial unloading stiffness (Fig. 9b). Sliding behaviour was instead described by an elastoplastic law with a limit force governed by a Mohr–Coulomb criterion (Fig. 9c).

Fig. 9 Constitutive law adopted for describing the masonry response in: **a)** rocking mechanism; **b)** shear mechanism; **c)** sliding mechanism

Through this modelling strategy, the numerical model can be calibrated using a limited number of macroscopic mechanical parameters, namely the normal and shear moduli, the tensile and compressive strengths and fracture energies, the diagonal shear strength and the characteristic shear strain associated with the softening branch, and finally the cohesion and friction coefficient controlling sliding behaviour.

The masonry parameters were initially calibrated on the basis of the available experimental evidence, including uniaxial and compression-shear tests performed in previous investigations in Pavia (Guerrini et al. 2017; Senaldi et al. 2020). The values derived from these tests are reported in the first column of Table 2, while the final values adopted in the numerical model are reported in the second column for direct comparison.

Table 2 Comparison between mechanical masonry parameters obtained from experimental tests (Guerrini et al. 2017) and those adopted in the numerical model

Masonry properties	Experimental values Test Pavia (2017)	Adopted values in HiStrA model
Specific Weight, W [$\frac{kN}{m^3}$]	19.8	19.8
Young modulus, E [MPa]	3462	200
Tensile strength, f_t [MPa]	0.17	0.05
Tensile fracture energy, G_t [$\frac{N}{mm}$]	//	0.001
Compressive strength, f_c [MPa]	1.3	1.3
Compressive fracture energy, G_c [$\frac{N}{mm}$]	//	0.1
Shear modulus, G [MPa]	1524* (1898**)	80
Shear strength, f_{v0} [MPa]	//	0.05
Cohesion, c [MPa]	0.233	0.068
Friction coefficient, ϕ [-]	//	0.7
* from vertical compression test		
** from diagonal compression tests		

The parameters not directly available from the experimental data were estimated through empirical relationships reported in the literature. In particular, the fracture energies in compression and tension were assumed equal to 0.1 N/mm and 0.001 N/mm, respectively, according to the indications of the CEB-FIP Model Code (1990). The friction coefficient was set equal to 0.7, consistently with values commonly adopted for pre-cracked mortar joints in historical masonry structures.

After this preliminary calibration stage, the material parameters were refined through an iterative trial-and-error procedure aimed at achieving a closer agreement with the experimental shaking table results. As shown in Table 2, the final calibration required a significant reduction in both the Young's modulus and the shear modulus with respect to the experimentally measured values. In particular, the adopted values are approximately equal to 30% of the minimum values suggested by NTC 2018 for irregular stone masonry. This reduction was introduced to account for the damage accumulated during the previous experimental runs, which was not explicitly simulated during the calibration phase. A similar reduction was also required for the tensile strength, which was lowered from the experimental value of 0.17 MPa to 0.05 MPa. Likewise, the cohesion was reduced from 0.233 MPa to 0.068 MPa, since the experimentally measured value appeared unrealistically high for a historical masonry typology characterised by weak mortar joints (Ghiassi and Milani, 2019). Overall, the comparison reported in Table 2 highlights the extent of the updating procedure and confirms that the final calibration is consistent with both code recommendations and previous literature (Lourenço and Gaetani, 2022), which suggest substantial reductions in the initial stiffness parameters in the presence of pre-existing damage.

The interface between the two units was calibrated separately by adopting an elastoplastic constitutive law with linear softening in compression and zero tensile strength. The elastic parameters were defined consistently with the other interfaces in the model, based on the Young's and shear moduli assigned to masonry. By contrast, the nonlinear parameters were specifically calibrated to reproduce the behaviour of the mortar joint. The interface shear strength was finally defined by adopting the same cohesion and friction coefficient values used for the masonry sliding mechanism.

Timber beams and lintels were modelled through an elastic isotropic law using mechanical properties representative of typical softwood timber. The adopted mechanical parameters are: specific weight $W=7,5$ KN/m³, Young's modulus $E=1300$ MPa, and shear modulus $G= 500$ MPa.

4.2. Sensitivity analysis

Following the calibration of the mechanical properties, a sensitivity analysis was performed in order to identify the influence of the main material parameters on the dynamic response of the structure. To evaluate their individual contribution, the most relevant parameters were varied independently within predefined intervals derived from their statistical properties, namely mean value μ , standard deviation s , and coefficient of variation (CoV). The adopted CoV values were selected by referring, where possible, to the recommendations of the updated Eurocode 8 - Part 3 (2025) for roughly dressed stone masonry with irregular wythes. When no specific normative indication was available, the corresponding values were assumed by the authors. The adopted CoVs

and the resulting variation intervals are reported in Table 3, where, for each parameter, the mean value, standard deviation, and lower and upper bounds considered in the sensitivity study are listed.

Table 3 COV adopted for the sensitivity analysis

Parameter	CoV	μ	s	X_{min}	X_{max}
f_c [MPa]	20% ¹	1.3	0.26	1.04	1.56
f_t [MPa]	19% ¹	0.05	0.01	0.0405	0.0595
f_{v0} [MPa]	21% ²	0.05	0.011	0.0395	0.0605
E [MPa]	17% ¹	200	34	166	234
G [MPa]	17% ¹	80	13.6	66.4	93.6
G_t [N/mm]	20% ²	0.001	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	//	0.0012
G_c [N/mm]	20% ²	0.1	0.02	0.08	0.12
γ_p [-]	20% ²	0.002	$4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.0016	0.0024
γ_u [-]	20% ²	0.004	$8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.0032	0.0048
c [MPa]	20% ²	0.068	0.014	0.054	0.082
1. Updated Eurocode 8-part 3 (2025) 2. Assumed by the authors					

As shown in the table, the investigated parameters include the compressive and tensile strengths, the diagonal shear strength, the elastic moduli, the fracture energies, the drift parameters governing the softening branch, and the cohesion. For each parameter, a nonlinear dynamic analysis corresponding to the final experimental run (2.1Y) was carried out. Sensitivity was quantified by considering the percentage difference between the maximum displacement values obtained by assigning the minimum and maximum values of the investigated parameter, measured at control point 57 (see Fig. 8). The results are summarised in Table 4, which reports the percentage variation in the maximum monitored displacement associated with the variation of each parameter within the ranges defined in Table 3.

Table 4 Percentage variation of the maximum displacement at the monitored node resulting from the variation of each mechanical parameter within the ranges defined

Parameter	f_c	f_t	f_{v0}	E	G	G_t	G_c	γ_p	γ_u	c
	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	N/mm	N/mm	-	-	MPa
Δ	1%	6%	8%	19%	6%	0.3%	0.01%	1%	0.3%	3%

As shown in Table 4, the parameters exerting the greatest influence on the structural response are the tensile strength, the diagonal shear strength, and the elastic moduli. In particular, the Young's modulus produces the largest variation in the maximum displacement, while tensile and shear strength also play a relevant role. By contrast, the remaining variables have a much more limited effect on the monitored displacement within the considered ranges. These results indicate that a reliable calibration of the elastic and strength parameters is

essential for achieving an accurate prediction of the dynamic response, whereas the influence of fracture energies, drift limits, and cohesion is comparatively less significant within the investigated intervals.

It should also be noted that, for the tensile fracture energy, the sensitivity was evaluated by comparing the mean value with the corresponding upper-bound value only. This choice was necessary because the lower-bound value led to numerical convergence problems during the analyses. Finally, Fig. 10 shows the hysteretic loops obtained at the monitored control point for the minimum and maximum values of the most influential parameters, thus providing a graphical interpretation of the trends summarised in Table 4.

Fig. 10 Hysteretic loops at the monitored node for the minimum and maximum values of the most significant mechanical parameters considered in the sensitivity analysis: **a)** f_t ; **b)** f_{v0} ; **c)** E ; **d)** G

5. Analysis results and comparison

A preliminary nonlinear static analysis has been first carried out under gravity loads. An eigenvalue analysis was subsequently performed to investigate the dynamic characteristics of the structure. The first four mode shapes are shown in Fig. 11, while the modal properties of the first ten modes are summarised in Table 5 in terms of natural period, natural frequency, and participating mass ratios in the longitudinal and transverse directions. As reported in Table 5, approximately 56% of the participating mass in the transverse direction is mainly associated with the first two vibration modes, characterised by frequencies of 7.11 Hz and 7.47 Hz,

respectively. By contrast, about 53% of the participating mass in the longitudinal direction is primarily mobilised by the third vibration mode, with a frequency of 8.81 Hz. The modal shapes shown in Fig. 11 indicate that the first and second modes are predominantly translational in the transverse direction and mainly involve Unit 1 and Unit 2 separately, whereas the third and fourth modes govern the response of both units and are mainly associated with longitudinal and transverse translation, respectively. These results, although related to the linear behaviour, provide useful insight into the dynamic interaction between the two units and support the interpretation of the subsequent nonlinear analyses.

Fig. 11 Modal shapes of the main modes

Table 5 Modal properties of the structure in terms of natural period, natural frequency, and percentage of participating mass in the longitudinal and transverse directions for the first ten vibration modes

Mode	Period	Frequency	M_x	M_y	ΣM_x	ΣM_y
[-]	[s]	[Hz]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]
1	0.140	7.11	21.74	0	21.74	0
2	0.130	7.47	33.73	0	55.47	0
3	0.110	8.81	0.00	52.46	55.47	52.46
4	0.087	11.49	6.77	0	62.24	52.46
5	0.082	12.20	0.66	0	62.91	52.46
6	0.081	12.36	0.0030	0.0012	62.91	52.46
7	0.081	12.37	0.0029	0	62.91	52.46
8	0.079	12.72	0.0036	0.0002	62.91	52.46
9	0.079	12.72	0.0001	0.0210	62.91	52.48
10	0.079	12.73	0.1800	0.0027	63.10	52.48

5.1. Nonlinear Pushover Analyses

Two nonlinear static pushover analyses were carried out in the longitudinal direction to compare the predicted collapse mechanisms with the experimental damage observed after Run 2.1Y, which was the last test performed before the strengthening intervention. The analyses were conducted in the positive Y direction, corresponding to the weakest direction of the specimen due to its irregular geometry in elevation. Two lateral load patterns were considered: one proportional to the mass distribution and the other proportional to the first significant vibration mode in the Y direction.

The deformed configurations obtained at the final step of the pushover analyses are reported in Fig. 12. As shown in Fig. 12a, the mass-proportional load distribution leads to a more global failure mode, involving also the first level of the structure. Although this analysis correctly identifies the source of vulnerability associated to the interface between the two units, the resulting collapse mechanism differs from the experimental one, which was dominated by a local out-of-plane mechanism involving the upper portion of Façade 4, as shown in Fig. 5. By contrast, the pushover analysis performed with mode-proportional forces, shown in Fig. 12b, provides a much closer agreement with the experimental response. In this case, the model predicts the out-of-plane overturning of the upper wall and reproduces more effectively the kinematic separation and damage pattern observed during the shaking table test. This comparison suggests that, for the analysed aggregate, a load distribution based on the modal shape is more representative of the actual dynamic behaviour than a mass-proportional pattern.

Fig. 12 Deformed configuration and colour map of the horizontal displacements in the Y direction corresponding to the final step of the pushover analyses conducted in the +Y direction applying lateral loads proportional to **a)** the masses and **b)** the fundamental mode in the same direction

In addition to the qualitative comparison of the failure modes, the pushover results were evaluated against the experimental evidence in terms of force–displacement response. Fig. 13 compares the experimental hysteretic loops with the numerical capacity curves obtained from the pushover analyses in the longitudinal direction, expressed in terms of base shear versus displacement at node 57, this latter target point well represents the OOP behaviour of the wall mainly involved on the failure mode.

Fig. 13 Comparison of the experimental hysteretic loops and numerical capacity curves in HiStrA at the control point

The results show that the pushover analysis performed with a modal load distribution is characterised by significantly lower lateral stiffness and strength than those observed experimentally. This behaviour is associated with the premature activation of a local OOP mechanism at the second storey. In particular, the concentration of lateral demand at the upper level triggers a local rocking mechanism of the façade before the shear capacity of the ground floor can be fully mobilised. By contrast, the mass-proportional pushover yields a capacity curve with higher stiffness and strength, in better agreement with the experimental hysteretic response, and leads to a more global failure mode involving both storeys of Unit 2.

Overall, these results indicate that conventional pushover analyses are not able to simultaneously reproduce the final observed collapse mechanism and the maximum base-shear capacity of irregular masonry aggregates under dynamic loading. For this reason, a nonlinear dynamic analysis of the aggregate was subsequently carried out, as described in the following section.

5.2. Dynamic Nonlinear Analyses

To reproduce the experimental response more realistically, seven nonlinear time-history analyses were performed following the shaking table loading protocol. The numerical simulations were carried out using the Newmark integration scheme, while Rayleigh damping was adopted with a damping ratio of 5% assigned to the second and third modes. The deformed configuration obtained after Run 2.1Y is shown in Fig. 14, where the colour map represents the horizontal displacement in the Y direction at the time step corresponding to the maximum longitudinal displacement. The numerical failure mode combines both IP and OOP damage and involves the upper and lower portions of Unit 2 as well as Façade 1 of Unit 1. The predicted mechanism is in reasonably good agreement with the experimental crack pattern reported in Fig. 5, confirming the ability of the model to capture the interaction between local and global response mechanisms.

A quantitative comparison between numerical and experimental results was carried out in terms of maximum longitudinal base shear. Fig. 15a reports the numerical and experimental peak values for all the analysed runs, while Fig. 15b compares the corresponding time histories for Run 2.1Y.

Fig. 14 Deformed configuration and colour map of the horizontal displacements in the Y direction at the time step 12.4 sec of the 2.1Y analysis, when the structure reached the maximum displacement U_y (at node 41).

Overall, the numerical model provides a satisfactory prediction of the global shear response. In most cases, the computed values slightly underestimate the experimental ones, with the only exception of Run 2.1Y, for which the model overestimates the peak base shear by about 9%. For the runs in the Y and XY directions, the differences are generally limited. For example, the discrepancy in Run 1.1Y is approximately 1%. Larger relative errors are observed for some X-direction runs, but these correspond to low absolute values of base shear and are therefore less significant in practical terms. The good agreement between the numerical and experimental time histories reported in Fig. 15b further confirms that the DMEM model is able to reproduce the global force response of the aggregate with satisfactory accuracy.

Fig. 15 a) Comparison of the experimental and numerical maximum V_{by} at each Run; **b)** Comparison of the experimental and numerical V_{by} time histories for Run 2.1Y

A more critical comparison emerges when displacements are considered. Fig. 16 reports the maximum displacements recorded at three representative control points, namely nodes 41, 57, and 48, as well as the maximum longitudinal opening of the interface between the two units, computed from the difference in

displacement between nodes 34 and 28. At low and moderate intensity levels, the numerical predictions are reasonably close to the experimental data. For instance, the discrepancy in the displacement of node 48 is about 10% in Run 1.1Y and 13% in Run 1.3XY. However, during the most severe excitation, corresponding to Run 2.1Y, the model significantly underestimates both the displacement demand and the interface opening. The differences reach 74% at node 41, 82% at node 57, 87% at node 48, and 94% for the maximum joint opening. These results indicate that, although the model captures the correct damage pattern and force response, it remains too stiff in the highly nonlinear range and is unable to reproduce the full displacement capacity observed experimentally.

The underestimation of the displacement response may be attributed to several factors. First, the macro-element mesh remains relatively coarse and may not fully describe the progressive interaction between IP and OOP wall mechanisms. Second, the simplified constitutive laws currently adopted in the model do not explicitly account for the high damage accumulation and stiffness degradation under repeated cyclic loading. Finally, the small-displacement assumption underlying the present DMEM formulation, even when P- Δ effects are considered (Cusmano et al. 2023), may contribute to limiting the numerical response in the last loading stages, when the experimental structure experienced large-amplitude displacements.

Fig. 16 Comparison of the experimental and numerical maximum displacement of: **a)** node 41; **b)** node 57; **c)** node 48; **d)** unit-to-unit opening at each Run

To further assess the role of damping in the displacement prediction, an additional sensitivity study was carried out by varying the viscous damping ratio. Three values were considered, namely 1%, 3%, and 5%, consistently with the assumptions adopted by other researchers in the blind prediction phase. Fig. 17a compares the hysteretic response at node 41 for the final run 2.1Y using the three damping values, while Fig. 17b–d compare each numerical response with the corresponding experimental loop. As expected, decreasing the damping ratio increases the computed peak displacement: for node 41, the maximum numerical displacement rises from 15.19 mm for 5% damping to 25.71 mm for 1% damping, corresponding to an increase of about 41%. Nevertheless, even the lowest damping ratio still leads to a substantial underestimation of the experimental peak value of 59.37 mm.

This confirms that the discrepancy cannot be explained solely by the damping assumption and is more likely related to intrinsic modelling limitations. For this reason, the reference value of 5% damping was retained in the remainder of the study, thereby ensuring consistency with the previously discussed analyses.

Fig. 17 a) Numerical hysteretic loops for node 41, during the Run 2.1Y analysis, for the different values of damping ratio; comparison of the hysteretic loops obtained from experimental testing and those obtained by the HiStrA numerical model at node 41 during the final test phase (Run 2.1Y) with: damping ratio **b)** 0.05; **c)** 0.03; **d)** 0.01.

5.3. Incremental Dynamic Analysis

Since the nonlinear dynamic analyses highlighted an overstrength of the numerical model and an underestimation of the displacement demand, an Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) was performed in order to investigate the response of the structure beyond the experimental loading protocol and to identify the ultimate PGA that the numerical model is able to sustain. The same seismic input adopted in Run 2.1Y, corresponding to the east–west component of the 1979 Montenegro earthquake applied in the longitudinal direction, was used as the reference signal. The analysis started from the experimental baseline PGA of 0.593g. For intensities above this value, the signal was progressively scaled up by means of a scale factor increment equal to 0.05 until a PGA of 1.7g was reached. For intensities below the baseline, the signal was scaled down with larger decrements, of 0.25, until approaching zero.

The IDA results are shown in Fig. 18a in terms of maximum displacement at node 57 as a function of the input PGA. The curve exhibits a nonlinear monotonic trend, which reflects the progressive evolution of the structural response under increasing seismic intensity. The same figure also reports the experimental peak displacements measured during the three longitudinal input runs, namely 0.1Y, 1.1Y, and 2.1Y. The comparison confirms that numerical and experimental results are fairly close at low PGA levels, whereas a marked divergence appears beyond approximately 0.2g, consistently with the trends already discussed in the nonlinear dynamic analyses. Thus, the IDA confirms that the model captures the initial stages of the response satisfactorily but progressively underestimates displacement demand as the structure enters the strongly nonlinear range.

To provide a more direct comparison in the force–displacement space, the IDA results were also interpreted in terms of a dynamic pushover curve. As shown in Fig. 18b, this curve was constructed by plotting the maximum longitudinal base shear values occurring within a ± 0.15 s time window centred on the instant of peak positive or negative displacement, again referred to node 57. The resulting dynamic pushover curve is compared with the experimental hysteretic loop of Run 2.1Y. Unlike the static pushover results, this representation incorporates inertia effects and therefore provides a more meaningful picture of the actual nonlinear force–displacement response under seismic excitation.

A more detailed interpretation of the IDA results is provided by Fig. 19, which reports the dynamic pushover curve of the aggregate together with the individual contributions of Unit 1 and Unit 2. This representation makes it possible to examine not only the global force–displacement response, but also the evolution of the relative contribution of the two interacting units as the seismic demand increases.

The overall response can be divided into three main stages. The first stage corresponds to an initial quasi-linear elastic branch up to a displacement of about 6.67 mm, in which the aggregate response remains nearly proportional to the input demand. In this range, both units contribute to the global stiffness, and the interaction between them does not yet produce significant nonlinear effects. The second stage extends up to a displacement of about 64.86 mm and is characterised by a progressive reduction in tangent stiffness. This branch marks the transition to a nonlinear regime, in which damage progressively develops and internal forces are redistributed between the two units. In particular, the contribution of Unit 1 tends to stabilise, whereas Unit 2 continues to mobilise increasing resistance. The third stage corresponds to a further nonlinear branch up to the end of the

analysis at 136.38 mm. In this phase, the response is mainly governed by the increasing contribution of Unit 2, while Unit 1 provides only a limited increment in resisting capacity. The curve then approaches the global peak strength, followed by the onset of softening.

Fig. 18 a) IDA curve and **b)** dynamic pushover curve and experimental hysteretic loop 2.1Y referred to node 57

The decomposition shown in Fig. 19 clearly demonstrates that the seismic response of the aggregate cannot be interpreted as the mere superposition of two independent structural systems. On the contrary, the contribution of each unit evolves continuously during the analysis, and the global response emerges from the mutual interaction between the two parts of the aggregate. The variation in the relative contribution of Unit 1 and Unit 2 confirms that the aggregate effect plays a decisive role not only in the initial stiffness and strength of the system, but also in the subsequent development of damage, in the redistribution of resisting mechanisms, and ultimately in the approach to global collapse. For this reason, the interpretation of the IDA through the dynamic pushover curve provides a particularly effective framework for better understanding the nonlinear seismic behaviour of masonry aggregates and the structural interdependence of their constituent units.

Fig. 19 Dynamic pushover curve of the aggregate structure and its constituent Unit 1 and Unit 2.

The quantitative contribution of the two units is further detailed in Table 6, which reports, for the most significant stages of the response, the PGA, maximum displacement, and base shear values sustained by each unit and by the aggregate as a whole. The ratio between the base shear contributions of the two units confirms that the interaction between Unit 1 and Unit 2 changes throughout the response history. In the initial elastic stage, both units contribute significantly to the global base shear, while at larger displacement levels the response becomes increasingly governed by Unit 2, which continues to mobilise strength even when Unit 1 has already reached a nearly constant contribution. This interpretation is consistent with the evolution of the damage pattern observed in the nonlinear dynamic simulations.

Table 6 Contribution in terms of longitudinal base shear of the aggregate and its constitutive units at each stage

Region	Elastic			Nonlinear Stage 1			Nonlinear Stage 2		
	$U_{y,max}$ [mm]	0.99	3.14	6.67	16.72	22.90	36.70	64.86	87.73
PGA	0.15g	0.30g	0.45g	0.67g	0.77g	0.89g	1.04g	1.31g	1.69g
$V_{by,max}^{Unit1}$ [kN]	15.41	28.22	40.74	50.97	60.92	60.90	55.32	63.18	67.60
$V_{by,max}^{Unit2}$ [kN]	18.46	36.37	53.75	76.19	82.49	97.17	105.27	116.68	119.05
$V_{by,max}^{TOTAL}$ [kN]	33.87	64.59	94.49	127.16	143.41	158.07	160.59	179.86	186.64
Δ [%]	83.48	77.61	75.80	66.89	73.86	62.67	52.55	54.15	56.78

Finally, the failure configurations associated with selected points along the IDA path are shown in Fig. 20. These results indicate that the collapse mechanism remains qualitatively consistent over the range of analysed scale factors, while the severity of the damage increases with the input intensity. The sequence of deformed shapes confirms the progressive evolution from an initial distributed response to the activation of more pronounced local and global mechanisms. This provides further support for the robustness of the model in predicting the local and global failure modes, even though the numerical displacement capacity remains lower than that observed experimentally.

Overall, the analyses presented in this section show that the DMEM model is capable of reproducing the main characteristics of the seismic response of the tested aggregate, particularly in terms of modal properties, failure mechanisms, and base shear demand. At the same time, the comparison with the experimental evidence clearly highlights the current limitations of the modelling strategy in the prediction of displacement demand and interface opening under severe seismic excitation.

Fig. 20 Deformed shapes of the structure obtained from nonlinear dynamic analyses under different $V_{by,max}^{TOTAL}$ values: **a)** 94.49 kN; **b)** 143.41 kN; **c)** 158.07 kN; **d)** 186.64 kN. The colour map indicates the maximum absolute displacements in the Y-direction

6. Conclusions

This study investigated the applicability of the Discrete Macro-Element Method (DMEM), implemented in the HiStrA software, for the seismic assessment of unreinforced masonry (URM) aggregate buildings through a post-diction analysis of the SERA-AIMS experimental campaign, conducted in 2021 at LNEC in Portugal. The benchmark case consisted of a half-scale stone masonry aggregate tested on a shaking table, providing a valuable reference for evaluating the capability of numerical models to reproduce the complex dynamic response of interacting structural units.

The results showed that the proposed modelling strategy is able to capture the main features of the global structural response with satisfactory accuracy. In particular, the DMEM model proved to be effective in reproducing the observed failure mechanisms, including the interaction between in-plane and out-of-plane responses, as well as the progressive activation of damage in the two constituent units. The comparison with the experimental evidence also showed a generally good agreement in terms of base shear response, confirming that the model can provide a reliable estimate of the global capacity of the aggregate under dynamic loading.

Although the model reproduced the experimental crack patterns and collapse trends with reasonable consistency, it systematically underestimated displacement demand and interface opening at higher seismic intensity levels. This discrepancy became more pronounced during the most severe loading stages, when the experimental response was characterised by significant nonlinear effects, progressive damage accumulation, and large displacement amplitudes. The sensitivity analysis further clarified the role of the main mechanical parameters in the seismic response of the aggregate. Among the investigated variables, the elastic moduli and the tensile and shear strengths were found to exert the strongest influence on the dynamic response, while the remaining parameters produced comparatively smaller variations within the considered ranges. This result confirms that the reliability of the numerical prediction is strongly dependent on the calibration of a limited set of mechanical properties, which therefore require particular attention when dealing with existing masonry structures.

The nonlinear static analyses also provided useful insight into the interpretation of the structural behaviour. The comparison between the pushover results and the experimental evidence showed that conventional static procedures may not be sufficient to simultaneously reproduce both the observed collapse mechanism and the actual base shear capacity of highly irregular masonry aggregates. In this respect, the dynamic analyses turned out to be more effective in describing the response of the benchmark specimen, especially in the presence of strong interaction between local and global mechanisms.

The Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) allowed a broader interpretation of the model response beyond the experimental loading protocol, highlighting the progressive evolution from the initial quasi-elastic stage to the nonlinear phase governed by stiffness degradation, force redistribution, and increasing participation of the two interacting units. The dynamic pushover interpretation derived from the IDA results also provided useful information on the contribution of each unit to the overall seismic response of the aggregate, showing that the interaction between the units plays a decisive role throughout the response history.

Overall, the study confirms that the DMEM approach represents a promising numerical strategy for the analysis of masonry aggregates, as it provides a favourable balance between computational efficiency and predictive capability. This aspect is particularly relevant for engineering-oriented applications, where simplified but reliable tools are needed for the assessment of large and geometrically complex existing building stocks. At the same time, the observed discrepancies in terms of displacement capacity indicate that further developments are required to improve the representation of damage evolution, interface behaviour, and large-displacement effects.

In conclusion, the present work provides a first validation of the DMEM approach for the nonlinear dynamic simulation of URM aggregate buildings against a well-documented experimental benchmark. The results support its use as a practical and robust tool for the seismic assessment of this structural typology, while also identifying the main aspects that should be addressed in future developments. In this sense, the study contributes to the ongoing effort to define reliable modelling strategies for masonry aggregates and to support future code-oriented procedures for their seismic assessment.

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